

THE STUDY OF THE PROBLEM OF PERSONALITY SOCIALIZATION AND PROFESSIONAL ADAPTATION IN PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract: This scientific article explores one of the pressing issues in modern psychology: the interconnection between the processes of an individual's socialization and their adaptation to professional activities. Drawing on psychological theories, the article analyzes how an individual's integration into society is inextricably linked to finding their place in a professional environment, mastering professional roles, and adapting to the socio-psychological climate of the work team.

Keywords: Personality, socialization, professional adaptation, socio-psychological climate, professional deformation, motivation, work team, professional identification, psychological mechanisms.

Personality socialization is one of the fundamental problems of psychology, sociology, and pedagogy, representing a complex and multifaceted process in which a person assimilates social experience and reproduces it in their activities. In scientific literature, the concept of "socialization" is interpreted within the framework of various approaches. According to the theories of scholars such as B.G. Ananyev, L.S. Vygotsky, S.L. Rubinstein, and A.N. Leontiev, personality socialization is not merely adaptation to the requirements of society (adaptation), but the process of an individual's active entry into the system of social relations and the transformation of internalized norms into their internal values (interiorization).

Professional socialization is an integral part of general socialization. E.F. Zeyer defines professional socialization as the process of an individual's adaptation to the requirements of a specific professional activity, as well as the assimilation of values, behavioral norms, and expectations inherent in that profession. In this process, an individual not only acquires professional knowledge but also develops a specific "professional identity." In his research on professional psychology, E.A. Klimov focuses

on the interaction between the individual and the profession, emphasizing that individual psychological characteristics play a decisive role in this complex dynamic process.

In psychology, the process of professional adaptation constantly proceeds in parallel with socialization. Professional adaptation is an individual's entry into a new production or service environment, adapting their psychophysiological and socio-psychological state to the requirements of new conditions. According to G.S. Nikiforov, professional adaptation is measured by three main criteria:

1. objective criterion - efficiency in service or labor activities (timely and high-quality performance of tasks);
2. subjective criterion - a person's sense of satisfaction with their activities and professional environment;
3. Psychophysiological criterion – the functioning of the human body and nervous system during activity without excessive strain.

Uzbek scientists E.G. Goziev, B.R. Kodirov, and G.B. Shoumarov studied the issues of youth socialization and their professional orientation under the influence of the national mentality, Eastern values, and social institutions (family, mahalla, educational institutions). As noted in their works, the socialization of the individual under the conditions of Uzbekistan proceeds based on the characteristics of collectivism. This creates a foundation for the unique formation of qualities such as duty, responsibility, and loyalty to the team in young people, including future military personnel.

However, unlike traditional professional socialization, the process of socialization in the military sphere has a number of sharp patterns. Military service is not an ordinary profession, but a social institution that requires an individual to subordinate their entire lifestyle, thinking, and even part of their personal freedoms to certain laws and rules. Relying on the conclusions of A.G. Karayani and P.A. Korchemny, it can be concluded that while in civilian specialties there are certain flexible boundaries between the employee and the employer, in the military system these boundaries are determined by strict statutory requirements and subordination. This requires a high level of psychological resilience and tolerance to frustration (obstacles) from the individual.

Thus, a psychological analysis of the problem of personality socialization and professional adaptation shows that this problem is much more complex than the acquisition of simple knowledge and skills. It requires a fundamental restructuring of the human motivational-need sphere, its value system, and behavioral models. Especially for a person entering the military sphere, this process is characterized by crisis, various psychological barriers and stress factors.

1.2. Specific features, patterns, and stages of military-professional socialization

Military-professional socialization is the process of a serviceman mastering the values, norms, and roles of the military environment and feeling themselves as a full member of that social group. This process differs fundamentally from ordinary professional socialization in that it occurs within the specific conditions of military service.

The most important features of military-professional socialization include:

First, the strict normality and hierarchy of the military environment. The behavior of a serviceman, his daily routine, and even his style of conversation are strictly limited by military statutes and regulations. In such conditions, socialization requires the individual to limit certain individual freedoms in the interests of the community and the state.

Secondly, the extreme nature of the activity and the high risk factor. Military activity is always conducted under the threat of combat training, weapons handling, field exercises, and emergency situations. Therefore, military-professional socialization involves not only knowledge of the rules but also the ability to control one's emotions even when life is in danger and the formation of psychological readiness to perform a combat mission.

Thirdly, a high level of teamwork. In military service, no task can be solved alone. The principle of "one for all, all for one" forms the basis of the socio-psychological climate within military units. Therefore, in individuals who are unable to adapt to the military community, are isolated, or have egocentric characteristics, the process of military socialization is difficult and often leads to neurotic disorders.

Military-professional socialization develops based on strict laws and stages. In modern military psychology, it is generally accepted to divide this process into the following four stages:

1. Initial (pre-conscription or pre-military) stage. This stage involves the formation of young people's initial perceptions of military service, patriotic feelings, and interest in the military profession within the family, school, and social environment. Within the framework of the concept of military-patriotic education of youth in the conditions of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to this stage at the state level.

2. Stage of primary military-professional socialization. This stage occurs in military educational institutions (higher military educational institutions, sergeant training schools) or during the first months of compulsory military service. This period is considered the most complex transitive (transitional) period. Because a cadet or a private abandons his former stereotypes of civilian life and falls into strict military discipline. During this period, an adaptive syndrome is observed in a person as a result of a feeling of "isolation," physical fatigue, and acclimatization to strict subordination. Mastery is mainly carried out under external control (under the influence of commanders).

3. The stage of active (professional) socialization. The period after a serviceman graduates from an educational institution or begins service under contract and is appointed to their position directly in military units. At this stage, an officer or sergeant tests their professional knowledge and leadership skills in practice. During this period, the center of socialization is no longer merely compliance with the charter, but the motivation to manage others, find one's place (authority) in the team, and grow through the career.

4. The stage of post-conscription resocialization. This is the process of a serviceman's reintegration into civil society after being discharged into the reserve or retirement. Empirical observations have proven that a sudden break from the military environment also causes many psychological problems.

Within the framework of this study, our primary focus is on the third stage—active (professional) socialization. This is because it is at this stage that military personnel face the most changes in their service status (change of position, transfer to another garrison, rotation, etc.). Each such change requires the individual to re-adapt and continue the socialization process in new conditions.

The continuous dynamics of military activity indicate that the service path of officers and sergeants is not uniform. According to the rules, due to operational necessity, military personnel are regularly rotated to various military units, districts, or regions, their positions are changed, or they are sent to extreme areas as part of combat training exercises. Each such change in the language of psychology is called a transitional state or a crisis point, and it directly affects the psyche of the serviceman.

From a psychological perspective, it is advisable to study the psychological impacts caused by changes in service status by dividing them into several groups:

1. Impact of changes in position (promotion or demotion). A new appointment, especially to a leadership position, is not only an increase in social status for a serviceman, but also a burden of extremely high psychological responsibility. In a new position, an officer may have to manage subordinates who are older or more experienced. This situation causes "status conflicts" and increased anxiety. In psychology, this is known as "leadership adaptation syndrome." If a serviceman lacks psychological preparation, such as self-confidence, communicative competence, and decision-making independence, they disrupt the microclimate, become irritable, and begin to use an authoritarian-aggressive style toward their subordinates. A demotion is an even more severe state of fructification, characterized by deep depression, apathy toward service, and a decline in one's self-esteem (deprivation).

2. Change of place of service (garrison, territory) and its socio-psychological consequences.

The transfer of a serviceman to another region serves as a strong stressor not only for him but also for his family members. A break occurs from the previous, accustomed environment (friends, a familiar territory, supportive social ties). Adaptation to the climatic conditions of a new place, the informal rules of a new community, and the requirements of a new command requires "secondary adaptation." The addition of family and domestic problems (children's transfer to a new school, spouse's change of workplace) further increases the emotional tension in the serviceman. According to statistical data, in the first three months of rotation, military personnel exhibit relatively high rates of decreased

concentration, irritability, and error tolerance. At this stage, the serviceman's positive "coping strategies" (ways of constructive problem-solving) are of great importance.

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